

Does Short-dated Options Introduction Mitigate Expiry Day Effects? Evidence from the Introduction of Weekly Index Options

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Abstract

High volatility in the stock market is often attributed to derivative expirations. The National Stock Exchange of India, largest derivatives exchange in the world by number of contracts traded, introduced weekly or short-dated derivatives in Feb 2019 to mitigate the expiration day effects. The study empirically examines the return and volatility data surrounding expiration days during the period before and after the introduction of weekly derivatives. First, for the period before the introduction of weekly contracts, the study gathers empirical evidence suggesting the presence of upward shift in price effects around expiration day and a transitory upward shift in volatility. Next, the study shows with a comprehensive time series analysis, these adverse expiration day effects disappear in the period after the introduction of weekly options. The paper concludes that the weekly, short-dated, contracts fill the gap in the market depth and are beneficial to the over all market welfare. As the weekly options are gaining popularity across the exchanges and investors, the study has important implications to the regulators and practitioners around the world.

Keywords: Volatility, Expiration Day, GARCH.

JEL Classification: G14, G1

I. INTRODUCTION

There exists extensive literature, both theoretical and empirical, which documents that the expiry of derivative contracts adversely affect the underlying spot market. This happens largely due to the unwinding operations of arbitragers destabilize the spot market in terms of volatility and volume and is termed in the literature as expiration-day or expiration-hour effects. See Stoll & Whaley, 1987, 1991 & 1997 among others for both developed and emerging markets. The Indian market experiences the quadruple witching day, index- as well as stock- futures and options contracts expire on the last Thursday of the month.

A large number of derivative transactions take place on this expiry day and the trading and manipulation activities of speculators and unwinding of cash positions by arbitrageurs in the spot market cause considerable distortion to price and volatility near the expiry day. In response to the ever-increasing pressure of derivative contracts on the spot market, the Indian stock market regulator, SEBI, introduced weekly, short-dated, options to mitigate the adverse effects of expiry day. The weekly options allow better participation by traders as they are required to pay low premiums over monthly options in which premiums are high and gamma risk i.e. the risk in long duration option contracts expiring in-the-money or out-of-the-money is extremely high. This raises an important question to answer that is of equal importance to the regulators, traders and investors: do shorter-dated options such as weeklies, reduce or eliminate adverse expiration effect of higher volatility on the expiry day? To the best of our knowledge, this question remains largely unaddressed in literature, and it calls for serious attention with the rapid advancement in the financial markets.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II presents the Indian Market context, reviews relevant literature and develops hypotheses of interest. Section III briefs about the data, and methodology employed, Section IV presents results, and discussion and Section V conclude the paper.

II. The Indian Market Context

The National Stock Exchange of India (NSE) is the world's largest derivatives exchange by number of contracts traded for third straight year from 2019 to 2021 as per the World Federation of Exchanges (WFE). Derivatives trading in India have expanded many folds amid financial inclusion awareness generation and robust regulation. The Indian market regulators have tried to keep up with the growing popularity of derivative segments by encouraging consistent financial innovations. One such attempt is the launch of the weekly index options on its benchmark index, NIFTY 50, on February 11th, 2019 and these weekly options have witnessed a meaningful rise in volumes. Weekly option contracts start on every Friday and expire on the next Thursday at market close, excluding the Thursday of the monthly expiry week. The expiry ranges from one to five weeks and allows arbitrage between one-week expiry and two-week expiry options. The strike interval, contract multiplier, tick size, price quotation, and trading hours for weekly options remain the same as that of the monthly options. The inception of weekly options facilitates the market participants to enjoy 52 expiries a year as against 12 monthly expiries. However, with the introduction of weekly options, the expiration day effect goes from a once-a-month effect (expiration days of the monthly options and futures) to a once-a-week effect (expiration days of weekly options).

The expiry day effects have been explained in literature as “temporary distortions” in the prices and volatility of underlying assets due to an order imbalance that occurs on the expiry day of the derivatives. One of the early pieces of evidence of the expiration day effects has been recorded by Klemkox (1978). Klemkox posits that a majority of options contracts are exercised in the expiration week as the traders lose the incentive of trading the options in the secondary market without earning a time premium. The author finds that the price behavior of the underlying security significantly changes near the option expiry. Officer and Trennepohl (1981), in a similar vein, diagnose a significant downward pressure on the prices of the asset in the last two days before the option expiry. Cinar (1987) offers one of the several explanations to this effect. The author illustrates that if the stock price is lower than the exercise price on expiry, then many call writers may decide to sell the stock in the market, which would put downward pressure on the spot price. Bose and Bhaumik (2007) presented similar evidence in the emerging Indian economy. The authors found a substantial rise in the volatility of returns of market index near the expiration day. In contrast, Stoll and Whaley (1997) refuted the occurrence of expiration day effects in Australia in the absence of evidence documenting significant price reversal on the expiry of the derivative. The school was joined by Chen and Williams (1994), Karolyi (1996). Kan (2011) explained the observed asymmetry in the findings of several scholars and stated that divergence in findings might be a consequence of the variations in different setups that are examined. Different countries have different days of expiry, different trading and settlement mechanism, differences in policy regimes such as restrictions on short-selling, and lastly, different macro-economic environment.

Researchers, who studied the Indian context, mostly affirmed the prevalence of expiration day effects in India. Vipul (2005) identifies a downward pressure on the spot prices before the expiry of futures and options in the NSE and records a reversal after the expiration day. Kamaiah and Sakthivel (2008) confirm the presence of positive abnormal returns during the period before the expiry of the stock futures. Nandan et al. (2014) analyzed the price-efficiency of CNX NIFTY Index Futures. They concluded that the instruments are vulnerable to overpricing and that the mispricing series tends to significantly change as the expiry approaches. We are hence guided by literature to believe that there is a significant pressure witnessed by spot markets on the expiration of derivatives in India.

In an extension to this research stream, one might be interested in examining the impact of shorter-dated options such as weeklies, which are becoming popular across the exchanges, on the spot volatility. Oikonomou et al. (2019) exploited the information content of weeklies and find that the implied variance of these options is a better predictor of the future weekly realized variance than not only monthly implied variance but also well-established time-series models of realized variance. Anderson et al. (2017) use the deep OTM weekly options as an indicator of a risk-neutral jump process and ATM options as a reflection of current spot volatility.

The authors posit that market participants are better able to avoid diffusive and jump risks via weekly options as the expected volatility and jump intensity do not vary much over a short tenure. In another study, Wen (2020) exploited the information content of weekly options to examine their influence on spot-volatility. On running a difference-in-difference analysis, the author concluded that the weekly stock options do not cause a significant variation in the crash risk or realized volatility of the underlying equity. Wen (2020) discusses the variation in the intensity of underlying stock price volatility before and after the introduction of weekly options but does not address a possible change in the volatility-evolution-process. In a recent study, Prachi and Kiran (2022) examine the impact of introduction of weekly contracts on the underlying volatility, by exploring the information linkage of volatility evolution process.

As the volumes of weekly options are increasing steadily across the exchanges, it is imperative to understand and assess the largely untouched question of expiry day effects with the advent of short-dated, weekly options. This paper uses a quasi-natural setup of NSE, largest derivatives exchange in terms of number of contracts traded, in introducing weekly index options on its benchmark index NIFTY50, to assess the possible reduction or elimination of adverse expiry day effects on return and volatility of the underlying index. Hence, we formulate the following competing hypotheses:

- H_0 The adverse expiry day effects either on the price or volatility of NIFTY50 index are reduced / mitigated with the introduction of weekly derivative contracts.
- H_a There is no change in the expiry day effects created by the expiry of NIFTY50 derivative contracts.

We try to test the above hypotheses by providing a detailed specification of return and volatility of NIFTY50 within the GARCH framework and is discussed in next section.

III. Data and Methodology

NSE introduced weekly derivative contracts on NIFTY50, which is a well-diversified index comprising of 50 stocks, on 11th Feb 2019. To examine the absence of expiry day effects with the introduction of weekly derivatives on NIFTY50, we consider two-year data surrounding the date of weekly derivatives introduction. We collect the daily closing prices of NIFTY50 index from NSE website (www.nseindia.com) from February 11, 2018 to February 10, 2020. The PRE period is the one-year before the event, from February 11, 2018 to February 10, 2019 and the POST period is the one-year after the event, from February 11, 2019, to February 10, 2020.

To examine the impact of expiry day on spot returns and volatility, we employ the Generalized Auto Regressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH) model proposed by Bollerslev (1986), which has been widely used in empirical finance

literature to capture the temporal dependency phenomena and time-varying nature of volatility. With GARCH framework, we intend to compare the NIFTY50 volatility on the expiry days with that of non-expiry days and see if there is any change after the onset of weekly derivative contracts.

Guided by the vast literature, the first step in GARCH modeling, we first remove any predictability associated with lagged returns by incorporating the appropriate number of AR and MA terms. To study the impact of expiration day on the conditional mean, we include a dummy, Exp_t , variable for the expiration day. Since we intend to verify the presence of price reversal, we also include another dummy for the trading day immediately after the expiration day. Further, we include an interactive dummy to identify the change in expiration day effects with weekly derivatives introduction. The conditional mean equation for NIFTY50 daily return series follows an ARMA process and is specified as follows:

$$R_t = \varphi_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \varphi_i R_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^m \theta_j \varepsilon_{t-j} + \nu Exp_t + \nu d * Post * Exp_t + n Next_t + nd * Post * Next_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

The standardized residuals obtained from Eq (1) will be subjected to test for possible presence of ARCH effects by looking at the significance of Ljung-Box statistic. The presence of ARCH effects calls for GARCH model, which is expressed in general form as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_t / \Omega_{t-1} &\sim N(0, h_t) \\ h_t &= \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_i \varepsilon_{t-i}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j h_{t-j} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Fitting the GARCH model on the daily returns of the NIFTY50 index pre, as well as post the launch of weekly options, facilitates insights about the variations in impact of expiry day effects in the two sub-periods. We examine this by interacting the Exp dummy coefficient with a dummy variable, D_t (0 for pre-period and 1 for post-period) in Eq (2) and is refined as follows.

$$h_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_i \varepsilon_{t-i}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j h_{t-j} + \delta_1 Exp_t + \delta_2 Next_t + \gamma_1 Exp_t * Dum + \gamma_2 Next_t * Dum \quad (3)$$

Note that the δ_1 and δ_2 coefficients correspond to the period before the introduction of weekly derivatives contracts and whereas γ_1 and γ_2 represent the incremental changes in Exp_t and $Next_t$ coefficients in the period after the introduction of weekly derivative contracts.

A positive (negative) significant value for δ_1 would suggest the presence of upward (downward) pressure on the expiration day volatility in the period before the introduction of weekly derivative contracts. Conditional variance during the expiration period. A positive (negative) significant δ_1 coupled with a negative (positive) significant δ_2 would imply that the shift in expiry day volatility is transient and is reversed immediately in the pre-weekly derivatives period. The negative γ_1 would indicate the

reduction or elimination of upward pressure on expiry day volatility with the start of weekly derivatives. Insignificant γ_1 and γ_2 coefficients imply that the introduction of weekly derivative contracts has no impact on the expiration day effects.

The conditional mean and variance parameters in Eq. (3) can be estimated using the QML technique of Bollerslev and Wooldridge (1992); for optimization, we use the Broyden, Fletcher, Goldfarb and Shanno (BFGS) quasi-Newton algorithm.

IV. Results and Discussions

We first present some basic descriptive statistics of the daily returns and volatility for NIFTY50 index in Table 1. The summary statistics of expiry and non-expiry days are presented separately for overall period, pre-weekly contracts period and post-weekly contracts period. The daily returns are continuous compounded returns calculated as log price relative. All the NIFTY50 daily return series are subjected to Augmented Dickey-Fuller tests and the null hypothesis of unit root is strongly rejected. The standard deviation of the returns on expiry days (0.87) is higher than that of non-expiry days (0.80) during the period before the introduction of weekly contracts. On the other side, in the post period of weekly contracts, the standard deviation of returns is not higher on the expiry days vis-à-vis on the non-expiry days.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

This table reports basic summary statistics for the daily continuous compounding returns of NIFTY50 index. Pre-period refers to one year before (i.e., from 11-02-2018 to 10-02-2019) and Post-period is one year after (i.e., from 11-02-2019 to 10-02-2020) the onset of weekly derivative contracts. Exp is the day of expiry of derivative contracts, typically, the last Thursday of every month and NonExp refers to all other days. Panel A presents basic descriptive summary statistics of NIFTY50 return series. Panel B presents the univariate hypothesis tests of change in underlying volatility (Exp vs NonExp in Pre- and Post periods) with a battery of five different variance comparison tests.

Panel A: Descriptive Summary Statistics						
Statistics	PreWeekly			PostWeekly		
	All	NonExp	Exp	All	NonExp	Exp
Mean	0.0153	0.0083	0.1522	0.0331	0.0341	0.0144
Median	0.0570	0.0570	0.0937	0.0335	0.0445	-0.0908
Maximum	2.2974	2.2974	1.6679	5.1825	5.1825	1.1386
Minimum	-2.7044	-2.7044	-0.9814	-2.5420	-2.5420	-0.8893
Std. Dev.	0.8037	0.8015	0.8701	0.8885	0.8975	0.7210
Skewness	-0.1872	-0.2191	0.3117	0.9722	0.9845	0.2620
Kurtosis	3.5597	3.6408	1.8847	8.0904	8.1364	1.7735
Jarque-Bera	4.6283	5.8518	0.8163	303.1132	293.7707	0.8895
LB(10)	23.2480			13.7600		
LB-sq(10)						
ADF Stat	-15.130			-14.560		

Panel B: Univariate Variance Comparison Tests

Univariate Hypothesis Test	PreWeekly		PostWeekly	
	Statistic	Prob	Statistic	Prob
F-test	1.1784	0.61	1.5498	0.42
Siegel-Tukey	0.8834	0.38	0.1107	0.91
Bartlett	0.1445	0.70	0.8594	0.35
Levene	0.4437	0.51	0.1405	0.71
Brown-Forsythe	0.4492	0.50	0.1893	0.66

The most relevant numbers in this table are the volatility, reported in Panel B, with a battery of five different volatility (between expiry and non-expiry days separately for Pre- and Post- periods) comparison tests. All the univariate hypothesis tests of variance comparison suggest that there is no significant upward pressure on volatility on the expiry days irrespective of weekly derivative contract’s introduction. However, note that the presence of significant LB statistics clubbed with excess kurtosis is compatible with the temporal dependency and volatility clustering phenomena in the returns; make univariate results based on hypothesis testing are not reliable. This warrants a comprehensive time-series analysis, it is imperative to ensure that the stylized features are captured in the analysis. This leads us to employ ARMA-GARCH framework.

Table 2: AR-GARCH Results

This table reports GARCH framework estimation results for daily returns of NIFTY50 index. Exp_t , dummy variable, takes on a value of zero on non-expiry days and a value of one on the days of expiry (last Thursday of the month). Next, dummy variable, takes on a value of 1 on the day immediately after expiry day and a value of zero otherwise. Dum_t , dummy variable, takes on a value of zero before (from 11-02-2018 to 10-02-2019: PRE period) and a value of one after (from 11-02-2019 to 10-02-2020: POST period) introduction of weekly derivative contracts. The equations are estimated with BFGS algorithm and robust standard errors are used.

$$R_t = \varphi_0 + \varphi_1 R_{t-1} + vExp_t + vd * Dum * Exp_t + nNext_t + nd * Dum * Next_t + \varepsilon_t$$

$$\varepsilon_t / \Omega_{t-1} \sim N(0, h_t)$$

$$h_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 + \beta_1 h_{t-1} + \delta_1 Exp_t + \delta_2 Next_t + \gamma_1 Exp_t * Dum + \gamma_2 Next_t * Du$$

Parameters		Estimate	StdError	t-stat
Mean Equation				
Intercept	ϕ_0	0.0398	0.04	1.05
EXP	u	0.3358	0.18	1.88*
NEXT	n	0.5873	0.15	3.99***
DUM*EXP	ud	-0.3564	0.25	-1.45
DUM*NEXT	nd	-0.4160	0.26	-1.57
AR(1)	ϕ_1	0.0681	0.05	1.43
Variance Equation				
Intercept	α_0	0.1579	0.04	4.38***
RESID(-1)^2	α_1	0.3280	0.10	3.22***
GARCH(-1)	β_1	0.4918	0.08	6.32***
EXP	δ_1	0.4994	0.23	2.17**
NEXT	δ_2	-0.3316	0.12	-2.76**
DUM*EXP	γ_1	-0.3924	0.21	-1.87*
DUM*NEXT	γ_2	0.4822	0.22	2.19**
Diagnostics				
Residual Mean			-0.0383	
Skewness			0.5517	
Kurtosis			6.4818	
Jarque-Bera			271.8038***	
LB (10)			13.4040	
LB ² (20)			4.5559	
LM ARCH F-statistic			0.4586	

We first estimate the conditional mean and variance as specified in Eq. (1) & (3) for daily return series; the corresponding results are reported in Table 2. On the basis of AIC model selection criteria, we choose the AR (1) – GARCH (1, 1) model. It can be observed that the estimated GARCH model is stable as the sum of $\alpha_1 + \beta_1$ is less than one. The portmanteau Ljung-Box statistics up to lag 10 for both residual and residual squares is insignificant suggesting that the fitted model captured well the time dependency in return and volatility. Further, the sign and size bias test statistics also do not indicate any significant degree of asymmetry in the residuals supporting the correct model specification for NIFTY50 return series. Now turning to the coefficients of interest: the expiration day dummy, $Exp(v)$, coefficient in conditional mean equation is positive and marginally significant in pre-period which (vd) turns as negative and marginally insignificant in the post-period. However, the Next (n), dummy coefficient for the day immediately after expiry is significant and positive in pre-period and (nd) insignificant in post period. This suggests that, during the period before the introduction of weekly contracts, there exists a significant upward price pressure on the expiry day and this pressure continues on the next day as well. And with the introduction of weekly contracts, the extent of upward price pressure declines although marginally insignificant.

Now from the results of variance equation, there exists a significant adverse expiry day effect on volatility in the pre-period. This is evident from significant increase

in volatility (δ_1) on expiry day and this high volatility is transient as it gets reversed immediately after the expiry (negative and significant Next, δ_2 , dummy). The interactive dummy coefficients (γ_1 and γ_2), representing incremental changes in post-weekly period, have opposite and significant coefficients. This implies that the adverse expiry day effect on volatility gets mitigated/reduces with the introduction of weekly derivative contracts.

If the spot market is deep enough and if liquidity suppliers are quick to respond to selling or buying pressure, then the price effects of large arbitrage unwinding will be small. The above empirical analysis reports that there exists price pressure and (or excess return) on the expiry day and next day and a temporary increase in volatility (rises on expiry day and reverses the next day) during the period before weekly derivatives introduction indicate that the market mechanisms in India are not well designed to offset surprise imbalances and there was a need to increase the depth of markets. However, with the timely introduction of weekly contracts by the market regulator, these adverse effects are reversed making the spot market more efficient. Thus, we conclude that Indian market experiences the expiry day like any other non-expiry day.

V. Conclusion

This study contributes to the expiry day effects literature by providing robust evidence on the disappearing adverse expiry effects with the introduction of short-dated, weekly, contracts. This paper examined the presence of expiration day adverse effects even after the introduction of, short-dated, weekly derivatives on NIFTY50.

The empirical analysis in this paper applies GARCH framework and suggests that introduction of weekly contracts tends to mitigate the adverse effects of expiration day and makes expiration day as a "No Event" day. One also needs to check for the presence of abnormal volumes and price manipulations around expiration day, which we leave it for future research. Further, weekly contracts attract information-led traders due to its lesser margin money and making prices absorb information faster and in turn making markets more efficient. The paper concludes that the weekly, short-dated, contracts fill the gap in the market depth and are beneficial to the overall market welfare.

As the weekly options are gaining popularity across the exchanges and investors, the study has important implications to the regulators and practitioners around the world. The adverse effects of expiry day are widely reported in all major developed markets and as well in emerging markets. High volatility on expiration day implies that the investors are not sure about the settlement price and as well it may be due to possible manipulative actions. The manipulation activities of speculators may be the central cause behind high volatility on the expiration of contracts. The market regulators, around the world, are very concerned and debating about various ways to

curb this undue high volatility on expiration day.

The possible measures include changing the length of contract, shift to physical settlement from cash settled contracts etc. The results presented in this study indicate the disappearance of expiration day effects with the introduction of weekly contracts, is a welcome feature for derivative markets around the world. The learnings from Indian experience of introducing weekly contracts go a long way for both developed and emerging markets. Further research may be undertaken in this domain is to re-examine this issue with high frequency intra-day data to capture the volatility dynamics throughout the trading day to bring out explicitly the potential factors responsible for the adverse effects of expiration day.

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